

**WAYS TO USE THE EXPERIENCE OF ADVANCED FOREIGN
COUNTRIES IN IMPROVING THE BUDGET SYSTEM (USING THE
EXAMPLE OF BUDGETS OF THE BUDGET SYSTEM)**

Sobitkhanovich Akmal Turdimakhamedkhan

master, The Banking and Finance Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan

The Government approved the main directions of budget policy for 2018 - 2020 (so-called the budget resolution) [9]. For the first time in the history of budgeting in Uzbekistan, medium-term budget planning will be introduced.

The approved budget resolution is a strategic document that defines the direction of public finances for priority reforms. This will put in place a plan for the country's economic development in the future and create the basis for systematic deep reforms. The transition from a one-year to three-year perspective of budget planning is not just a technical change in budget formation by adding two more budget periods in the calculations. This is a systemic change in budget policy that should provide a strategic approach to identifying priority measures and an efficient allocation of the resources.

The foreign experience of using budgeting as one of the technologies of public finance management suggests that it alone cannot exist without a systematic approach, since it focuses on certain results from the using of budget funds. In turn, the effective result is virtually impossible to achieve solely due to budgeting technologies, since these are interrelated measures, and finances only serve their implementation. That is why in most foreign countries, budgeting technology was introduced at the same time as structural changes, or immediately after their implementation. And first and foremost, the whole system of public administration was reformed in order to increase the responsibility of government institutions for the results of its activities (Australia, New Zealand, Great Britain, the United States, etc.).

The methods (The technologies) of budget management in foreign countries have

recently evolved quite rapidly: from the traditional budget, the budget from results (implementation), basic budgeting, budgeting on a zero basis, budgeting «sunset» to the budget based on targeted programs (priorities). All innovations after the traditional budget (cost or item) are considered as components of the program-target method of budgeting [10].

The program-based budgeting method at the state level was first used in the United States to develop the Ministry of Defense estimates. The practice of using this method indicates its advantages compared with other methods used in the process of drafting budgets. This contributed to the application of the program-target method of budget planning in world practice.

It is actually for Uzbekistan the studying of the experience of using the program-target method of budget planning in the EU countries, such as, Great Britain, France, Italy, and Germany.

The experience of France in organizing the training of new principles of the program-target method of employees involved in the implementation of its main elements can be useful to Uzbekistan. So, in 2003, in order to implement the budget reform within the Institute of State Management and Development of Economy (ISMDE), a separate department was set up, whose function was to support the reforms in the ministries. The Institute of State Management and Development of Economy has developed three stages of training for employees of ministries and departments that are involved in the implementation of the program-target method in any way. All three wave studies took place between 2003 and 2006 during the transition period preceding the implementation of the LOLF [11].

The world practice highlights the following key elements of program budgeting:

- a strategic planning of the activity of public authorities and its component - financial strategic planning;
- a medium-term budgeting, which defines certain time fiscal frameworks for optimal resource allocation in the medium-term program;
- a system for monitoring and evaluating budget programs and the results of their

performers (strategic plans are the basis for the latter) [1].

The conclusions. Given the foreign experience of introducing systemic changes in fiscal policy for Uzbekistan, we are confident that the application of the program-targeted method will help to make the best choice of the priority budget policy for the medium-term perspective and ensure the achievement of positive results with the using of the budget funds. Improvement of the program-target method of expenditure planning will improve the quality of budget policy formulation of prioritization when allocating a limited amount of expenditures, increase the level of efficiency of using budget allocations, and facilitate streamlining of the activities of the main spending unit manager in executing budget programs. Strengthening the quality level of domestic budget policy, taking into account relevant world experience, will contribute to effective institutional transformation of social development.

References

1. Bugaj T.V., Galyuta A.A. Programno-cil'ovyy`j metod u byudzhetnomu procesi: zarubizhny`j dosvid i mozhly`vosti jogo vy`kory`stannya v Ukrayini [Program-target method in the budget process: foreign experience and possibilities of its use in Uzbekistan] // Visny`k Zhy`tomy`rs`kogo texnologichnogo universy`tetu. – 2011. – No 3(57). – S. 206–210. – Bibliogr.: 8 nazv.
2. Bulgakova S.O., Baranovs`ky`j O.I., Kucher G.V. Byudzhetna sy`stema Ukrayiny` ta Yevrosoyuzu [Budget system of Uzbekistan and the European Union] : monografiya ; M-vo osvity` i nauky` Ukrayiny` ; za zag. red. A.A. Mazaraki. – K. : Ky`yiv. nacz. torg.-ekon. un-t, 2009. – 409 c. – Bibliogr.: s. 404-409.
3. Bjudzhetnyj kodeks Ukrai'ny [Budget Code of Uzbekistan] (2010). Vidomosti Verhovnoi` Rady Ukrai'ny(VVR), 50-51. : <http://zakon5.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2456-17>. (last access: 01.02.2017).